

Influence of Implementation of Quality Management Practices on Operational Performance of Technical and Vocational Education and Training Institutions in the Sri Lanka - Study focuses on North Central Province

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Abstract: The purpose of the research study was to explore the Influence of Implementation of Quality Management Practices (QMP) on Operational Performance (OP) of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) Institutions in Sri Lanka and the study focuses on North Central Province (NCP). QMP can be defined as a systematic approach to improvement of quality in organizations business processes. The aim of improving the performance is all about of its service quality, profitability, customer satisfaction, and productivity. The TVET includes the process of skill-development of the workforce working in the industry of a country. After the implementation of QMP in the organizations then later organizations' management faced an issue, that there is a problem of low operational performance in (TVET) Institutions in many provinces. In the research study participated 202 students in many trade courses at TVET Institutions in NCP and a questionnaire used to gather data of QMP in the institution, student satisfaction and service quality. The results were analyzed using the SPSS software and used descriptive analysis, multiple regression analysis, correlations and t-test as analytical tools. Results revealed that there is a poor relationship between operational performance and customer focus and communication. However, the QMPs such as Employee Involvement and Continuous Improvement verified strong and significant relationship. It indicates that these TVET Institutions are not properly applying the QMP such as customer focus and communication in their institutions. Furthermore, this study recommended that TVET Institutions have to improve more on customer focus and communication.

Keywords: *Quality Management Practices, Operational Performance, Communication, Customer Focus, Continuous Improvement*

I. INTRODUCTION

This study mainly focuses on impact of implementation of the quality management practices (QMP) on operational performance (OP) in Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) institutions in the North Central Province (NCP). Operational Performance is defined as the process of measuring the efficiency and effectiveness of the organization. Effectiveness discusses the amount to which customer requirements are met; although efficiency is a measure of how economically to firm resources are utilized when providing customer satisfaction. Effective implementation of Total Quality Management (TQM) approach will increase Operational Performance with ensures that organizations change how they do activities to cut inefficiency, improve customer satisfaction and do the best practice.

Operational Performance and its quality of providing service is the most significant aspect whatever organization either production or service. Mainly operational performance is depending on the external environment drivers. Those external drivers are making competition and powerful of the among the industry competitors. TQM practices are one of the most effective methods for businesses to increase operational performance. Even though it was a long

time ago this subject is still vital these days because quality management systems are effective and scientists are still researching about this question (Priede, 2012).

Sri Lankan modern education system has started because of the country's integration into the Britain in the 19th century. As a result, the British towards the end of the 19th century set up Tertiary Education Institutes. Schools of other religious values were also established in later. The country's education structure can be divided into five main parts such as primary, senior secondary, junior secondary, collegiate and tertiary.

Under the secondary education, technical and vocational education which prepares individuals for the jobs that is built on manual or practical activities. Vocational and technical education seems not to be performing well in the production of competent and skilled graduates for socioeconomic, industrial and technological development of the nation. Idialu (2007) indicated that the quality as standards of in something as measured to other things that are the amount of goodness. Also he remarked that quality in vocational and technical education ensures that students have the knowledge, skills, competencies and understanding that are suitable for their area of responsibility.

The TQM approach to running vocational and technical education is being advocated in Sri Lanka because the world has become a global village with extremely dynamic technology and depleting resources. Since the vocational education historically rooted to prepare learners to perform to their fullest potential in such globalize and competing world, therefore, the technical and vocational education itself must be vibrant and adaptable.

Okunamiri (2002) stated that management practices are essential in education, including vocational and technical education. Especially in developing countries where the paucity of data and the unreliability of their collection, shortage of qualified data processing facilities and personnel, coupled with the urgency of providing quality education, call for the careful systematic use of available resources.

Then the many TVET institutions have implemented Quality Management System (QMS) and now currently, systems are being used by the TVET institutions in Sri Lanka. Many TVET institutions' management considers that there is a big issue of low operational performance in their institutions. Their managements are facing an issue of how to improve operational performance after implementing the TQM approach in their organization. Operational performance can be influenced by customer satisfaction, employee satisfaction, quality of service and many more.

In TVET institutions reports say some areas of operational performance are not good for many reasons. In TVET institutions, employee satisfaction is also low due to a few reasons. The service quality may have affected in different matters in the TVET institutions. Therefore TVET institution's management expects implementation of Quality Management Practices will growth Operational Performance and makes sure that may change and get benefited to activities that improve customer satisfaction. Quality management practices may improve TVET institutions services to meet customer requirements and expectations according to ISO standards. This research study only focuses on Sri Lankan technical and vocational education sector. There are few TVET institutions have implemented QMP in their institutions. This research study aim is to find the influence of implementing quality management practices on the operational performance in TVET institutions in the NCP.

II. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

2.1. Primary Objective

Study the influence of implementation of quality management practices on operational performance in the Technical and Vocational Education and Training institutions in Sri Lanka and study focuses to NCP.

2.2. Secondary Objectives

- To study the relationship between quality management practices and operational performance in TVET institutions in NCP.
- To study the relationship between customer focus and operational performance in TVET institutions in NCP.
- To study the relationship between communication and operational performance in TVET institutions in NCP.
- To study the relationship between employee involvement and operational performance in TVET institutions in NCP.

- To study the relationship between continuous improvement and operational performance in TVET institutions in NCP.
- To study the relationship between demographic characteristics and operational performance in TVET institutions in NCP.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1. Total Quality Management(TQM) Practices

TQM Principles define a management system in which an organization achieves organizational improvement over a commitment to customer needs. If any organization meets those requirements, then it allows every employee to maintain high values and make every effort for continuous improvement in the organization. TQM Practices are used in many quality management systems, such as Six Sigma, Lean, and ISO.

Al-Ali (2007) Said that TQM is the interaction to get a high quality output from the inputs such as individuals, policies, methods, and instruments. It is can be defined as a management philosophy with a complete collection of tools and methods to the purposes of implementation.

According to the quality management practices certain numbers of quality principles that most corporations should follow to make an effective TQM implementation. According to Flynn et al. (1994), there are some key principles of TQM such as Top management support, quality information, process management, product design, workforce management, supplier involvement and also customer involvement. furthermore, Black and Porter (1996) have presented other principles for TQM such as improvement measurement systems, people and customer management, operational quality planning, external interface management, supplier partnerships, teamwork structures, customer satisfaction orientation and communication of improvement information. Ahire et al. (1996) Showed that TQM Practices consists with employee involvement, employee training, design quality management, employee empowerment, product quality, and top management commitment.

Then later Sun (2000) and Motwani (2001) have introduced new principles for TQM as leadership, strategic planning, customer focus, information and analysis, people management, process management, and supplier management. After that, Al-Damen (2009) has found a new model named Jordan Business Excellence Model (JEBEM). It has the six major excellence criteria such as leadership, customer & market focus, strategic management, resources (human resources, information, financial, and materials), process and finally the business results.

In conclusion, according to International Standards Organization's (ISO) quality management principles defined as Customer focus, Leadership, Engagement of people, Process approach, Improvement, Evidence-based decision making, Relationship management.

3.2. Total Quality Management practices on operational performance

3.2.1. TQM practices on operational performance

TQM has been widely regarded as a tool for improving performance through measures with such as quality of the service. Operational Performances such as customer satisfaction, people satisfaction, quality of service impact on total quality management practices (Samson and Terziovski, 1999). The effective implementation of quality management principles increases customer satisfaction with the service contributions (Dale et al., 2001). Lee and Park (2016) indicated that quality management practices and competitive priorities can increase operational performance. Furthermore, manufacturing systems and quality management practices are found to be vital in sustaining competitive advantages.

The administrators of organizations should use the TQM principles on improving organizational processes and inputs to extend the quality. Increased quality would lead to customer loyalty and long-range profits will inexorably follow (Scholtes and Hacquebord, 2002). Vasantharayalu and Pal (2016) stated TQM practices in both service and manufacturing trades is required to sustain the quality of the work as well as improve the competition level in society. Also Saleh and Sweis (2018) explained the reality that, organizations which depend on customers to recognize their needs and consider their satisfaction is important for long period performance and satisfy or exceed their wants and hopes can produce better quality performance.

TQM generally improves effectiveness of production, creates high quality products, customers are more satisfied, leading to increased revenue and profit for companies (Kiprotich et al., 2018). Though there are, results have shown about TQM practices and operational performance. Some researchers used the same dimensions to study the relationship between TQM practices and operational performance, but they found dissimilar outcomes.

H1: The quality management practices have a relationship with the Operational Performance of TVET institutions in the NCP.

3.2.2. Customer Focus On Operational Performance

Customer focus has been defined as the amount to which organizations continuously satisfies their customer's needs and expectations (Zhang, 2000). Also Bank (1992) said another important thing is that Customer focus is the primary feature of TQM principles. An organization can be succeeded when it considers satisfying the customer needs in a dynamic business environment (Sila, 2007). Therefore, customer relationship management is to measure the customer satisfaction and act according to the results. Lee et al. (2003) did their studies to study the role of TQM practices in confirming customer satisfaction. They founded that quality management represented as key measures of customer satisfaction needs and customer needs change time to time.

H1a: The Customer Focus has a relationship with the Operational Performance of TVET institutions in the NCP.

3.2.3. Communication On Operational Performance

The TQM principle Communication shows an essential part in TQM practices as it forces employees and improves their team spirit in the organization during day today activities. Because of this practice of TQM, it is strong that understanding thoughts, state of mind and behavior of people arranged out under TQM practices and shared among these individuals through interaction and communication (Bisgaard, 2000).The Communication supports an organization to express who they are in the organization. The TQM practices of an organization always successful when customers are pleased with quality communication of the organization. Hence, the amount of success in organization TQM practices are measured based on its communication abilities.

H1b: The Communication has a relationship with the Operational Performance of TVET institutions in the NCP.

3.2.4. Employee Involvement On Operational Performance

TQM practices implementation process was recommended by Prajogo and Sohal (2006) integrated employees are most important in better improvement in any organizational performance. Delaney and Huselid (1996) discovered ideal human resources strategies influence TQM practices in the firm that in the end affects performance. The typical contribution is a process for enabling workers to take an interest in managerial basic leadership and change workouts and good to their levels in the association (Sundstrom et al., 1990).Training of employees and also making them contribute in decision-making processes and sharing of organization information increases productivity and confirms free interaction between employees and the management. The employees can use their skills and resources to increase the performance of the organization because they also get the benefits of the success. Taylor and Wright (2003) remarked that it as well is ending up progressively prominent. One acceptability, as proposed by Quality Management System programs, is that employee contribution is best idea of as an action which supports a Quality Management.

H1c: The Employee Involvement has a relationship with the Operational Performance of TVET institutions in the NCP.

3.2.5. Continuous Improvement On Operational Performance

A one of key practices of TQM principle is continual improvement. Anderson et al. (1994) has identified Organizations that practice TQM always set work processes that help to reduce faults and wastes during manufacture process and from now on, the TQM has improved the effectiveness of the organization. Additionally, Spencer (1994) defined good implementation of TQM which helps to extend the chances of great performance within the organization. Afterwards, Employees of the business organization are encouraged to use innovations and new manufacture methods through the implementation of continuous improvement procedures (Prajogo and Sohal, 2006).

H1d: The Continues Improvement has a relationship with the Operational Performance of TVET institutions in the NCP.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1. Research Design

The research study method of this research is descriptive and quantitative and it includes analysis of numerical data. The selected research method is using a survey type Descriptive Research Method. The aim is to categorize features, count them, and create statistical models in an effort to explain what is observed. Descriptive research includes collecting data which describe procedures then arranges, represents and describes the data (Glass and Hopkins, 1984). In survey method research participants may answer questions managed through interviews or questionnaires (Hale, 2011). Quantitative data are better organized and able to test hypotheses and all aspects of the study are sensibly designed before data is collected.

4.2. Conceptual framework

Source: Author Compilation

Fig.1-1 Conceptual framework of the research study

4.3. Research Variables

- i. **Independent variable(s)** : Quality Management Practices(QMP)
(Dimensions: Customer Focus, Employee Involvement, Communication, Continuous Improvement)
- ii. **Dependent variable** :Operational Performance
(Dimensions: Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction)
- iii. **Control Variables** : Demographic characteristics

4.4. Population

The target population of this study covered with 588 students who are studying in TVET institutions in the NCP. The students in training institutions include both males and females. These data are used to study the influence of implementing quality management practices on the operational performance of the TVET institutions in the NCP. Therefore, it was decided to apply this research study for Anuradhapura and Polonnaruwa districts in NCP Sri Lanka. 10 institutions selected from Anuradhapura and 6 institutions from Polonnaruwa.

4.5. Sample

In this research study, the sample was selected from students of TVET institutions in the NCP by using simple random sampling method under the probability sampling type. For this research study, 202 students were selected out of 588 from the TVET institutions in the NCP as sample size. Also 122 students were selected out of 406 from Anuradhapura and 80 students selected out of 182 from Polonnaruwa.

4.6. Data Collection Procedure

In the questionnaire drop and pick, technique was chosen for questionnaire administration to give respondents enough time to give well understood out responses. This enabled the researcher to establish understanding, clarify the purpose of the research study and the meaning of items that may not be clear. Students are the unit of analysis in this research study and questionnaire method was used to get data for the research. The researcher used non-contrived settings (without controlling the environment) to gather information from the students. The target respondents were students of TVET institutions. Closed questions were used in the questionnaire. TVET institutions in Anuradhapura and Polonnaruwa districts visited to collect data from full time students.

4.7. Method of Analysis

Research study data were checked for completeness and consistency after the gathering from TVET institutions. In here, both qualitative and quantitative methods were used for data analysis. So quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, standard deviation, frequency, mean and percentages to recognize major designs and profile characteristics of the data and multiple regression analysis using statistical package for social scientists (SPSS version 21). In this study, multiple regression analysis was used to decide the relationship between quality management practices and operational performance of TVET institutions in the NCP. The research model used for this study was in the form of;

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1+ \beta_2X_2+ \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + e$$

Where Y is the dependent variable Operational Performance, X is the independent variable Quality Management practices. β_0 is the Y intercept. $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ and β_4 are the coefficients of the variables; $X_1 =$ Customer focus, $X_2 =$ Communication, $X_3 =$ Employee involvement, $X_4 =$ Continues improvement and e = Standard error. Also, descriptive analysis and uses for to identify the basic nature of the research variables, and calculate the statistics such as mean, mode and etc. Then Correlation Analysis was used for finding the relationship between key research variables. Then next regression analysis uses to do like as Correlation Analysis to find those relationships among research variables.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1. Introduction

In here the results and discussions along with the key findings, concerning the research objectives of the research study which discussed about the research regarding the Influence of Implementation of Quality Management Practices on Operational Performance of TVET Institutions in the NCP. Various analysis methods were performed for each variable in the research and presented in tables. Then, finally, the hypotheses were tested and the results were discussed later.

5.2. Descriptive statistics of demographic factors

Table 1-1 Descriptive statistics results of demographic factors

Demographic factors		Frequency	Percent	Between Groups Sig.
District	Anuradhapura	122	60.4	0.527
	Polonnaruwa	80	39.6	
	Total	202	100.0	
Gender	Male	140	69.3	0.024
	Female	62	30.7	
	Total	202	100.0	

Age	Below 18 years	39	19.3	0.011
	18-25 years	143	70.8	
	25-35 years	12	5.9	
	35 above	8	4.0	
	Total	202	100.0	
Level of Education	Other	9	4.5	0.000
	O/L	83	41.1	
	A/L	110	54.5	
	Total	202	100.0	
Course Duration	6 Months	77	38.1	0.320
	12 Months	125	61.9	
	Total	202	100.0	
Distance from home to Center	<10 km	68	33.7	0.042
	11-24 km	64	31.7	
	25-35 km	10	5.0	
	> 35 km	60	29.7	
	Total	202	100.0	

(Source: Research Data, 2019)

5.2.1. Studying District

Participant’s data concerning their district are presented in Table 1-1, which was obtained by asking the participants to indicate their district. The study included participants who were from Anuradhapura district 60.4%, while other participants were from Polonnaruwa district 39.6%. This implies majority of the participants in this study from Anuradhapura District. Independent sample t-test p-value (0.527>0.05) shows that there is no significant difference in the means of Anuradhapura District and Polonnaruwa district.

Table 1-2 Independent Samples Test for Studying District

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Operational Performance	Equal variances assumed	13.166	0.000	0.633	200	0.527	0.0645	0.1018	-0.1362	0.2652
	Equal variances not assumed			0.594	133.32	0.553	0.0645	0.1085	-0.1501	0.2791

(Source: Research Data, 2019)

5.2.2. Gender

Participants’ data concerning their gender is presented in Table 1-3 that was obtained by asking the participants to indicate their gender. The study included male participants who were 69.3%, while female participants were 30.7%. This implies majority of the participants in this study were male. Independent sample t-test p-value (0.024<0.05) shows that there is a significant difference in the means of Male and Female students. In data analysis found male group higher than female group.

Table 1-3 Independent Samples Test for Gender

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		T-Test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Operational Performance	Equal variances assumed	0.486	0.486	2.275	200	0.024	0.2428	0.1067	0.0324	0.4531
	Equal variances not assumed			2.335	124.39	0.021	0.2428	0.1040	0.0370	0.4485

(Source: Research Data, 2019)

5.2.3. Age Categories

According to the one-way ANOVA, equity of variance is assumed (0.231>0.05) and there were differences between groups of the age categories (0.011<0.05).

5.2.4. Education level categories

According to the one-way ANOVA, equity of variance is assumed (0.328>0.05) and there were differences between groups of the course duration categories (0.00<0.05).

5.2.5. Course duration

According to the one-way ANOVA, equity of variance is assumed (0.053>0.05) and there were no differences between groups of the course duration categories (0.320>0.05).

5.2.6. Distance to center from home

According to the one-way ANOVA, equity of variance is assumed (0.316>0.05) and there were differences between groups of the distance to center categories (0.042<0.05).

5.3. The Reliability of Scale Items

To improve the reliability the pilot test was done on twenty-five respondents from a vocational training center in Anuradhapura district using questionnaires. The results from the pilot study used to address any deficiencies in the research instruments.

Table 1-4 Reliability of Research Items

Construct	No of Questions	Cronbach Alpha Coefficient
Customer Focus	6	0.714
Employee Involvement	6	0.867
Communication	5	0.807
Continuous Improvement	5	0.841
Student Satisfaction	8	0.884
Service Quality	14	0.917

(Source: Research Data, 2019)

According to the values of Table 1-4 reliability study illustrations that the reliable values for the variables Customer Focus (0.714) Employee Involvement(0.867), Communication (0.807), Continuous Improvement (0.841) ,Student Satisfaction (0.884),Service Quality(0.917). All alpha values are higher than the level of 0.7 of thumb mark(Gliem and Gliem, 2003).Therefore, all the variables have been constructed in good and reliable.

5.4. Discriminant Validity Tests

Table 1-5 Correlation Matrix of Variables

		Correlations						
Hypothesis			QMP	Customer Focus (CF)	Communication (Com)	Employee Involvement (EI)	Continuous Improvement (CI)	Operational Performance (OP)
	QMP	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	1					
H1a	CF	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	0.829**	1				
			0.000					
H1b	Com	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	0.866**	0.634**	1			
			0.000	0.000				
H1c	EI	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	0.875**	0.658**	0.654**	1		
			0.000	0.000	0.000			
H1d	CI	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	0.869**	0.609**	0.728**	0.642**	1	
			0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000		
H1	OP	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	0.842**	0.635**	0.638**	0.830**	0.758**	1
			0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).
 (Source: Research Data, 2019)

According to the Table 1-5 the Continuous Improvement and Operational Performance significantly correlated (r = 0.758). In addition, Communication and Operational Performance are significantly correlated (r = 0.638). The highest correlations between Employee Involvement and Operational Performance (r=0.830) and the lowest relationship between Customer Focus and Operational Performance (r=0.635). Finally, QMP and Operational Performance are significantly correlated (r = 0.842). The other remaining relationship between independents and Operational Performance effectiveness are positive manner. The other remaining relationships are also positive and significant.

5.5. Multiple Linear Regression

Table 1-6 Multiple Regression Analysis of four variables on OP

Predictor	Beta	Std. Error	T - Value	Sig.	Durbin-Watson	VIF	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
							Lower Bound	Upper Bound
(Constant)	0.778	0.148	5.266	0.000			0.487	1.069
Customer Focus	0.050	0.051	0.978	0.329		2.081	-0.051	0.151
Employee Involvement	0.458	0.039	11.632	0.000	1.491	2.237	0.380	0.535
Communication	-0.070	0.056	-1.250	0.213		2.575	-0.180	0.040
Continuous Improvement	0.352	0.046	7.669	0.000		2.442	0.262	0.443

(Source: Research Data, 2019)

Table 1-7 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	0.882	0.778	0.773	0.33658	1.491

a. Predictors: (Constant), Continuous Improvement, Customer Focus, Employee Involvement, Communication

b. Dependent Variable: Operational Performance

(Source: Research Data ,2019)

According to the above Table 1-6 the multiple regression stated that there are not significant relationships between the QMP Customer Focus, Employee Involvement, Communication, Continuous Improvement and Operational Performance of TVET Institutions. According to the analysis, R square was 0.773 and the observed level of significance approximately 77.3% explains the above relationship. The Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.491 is not too far from 2. The 95% confidence interval (CI) for Customer Focus and Communication are not significant predictors, but Continuous Improvement and Employee Involvement are significant predictors. Customer Focus (p=0.329) and Communication (p=0.213) have higher p values than 0.05. However, Continuous Improvement (p=0.00) and Employee Involvement (p=0.00) have p values less than 0.05. But According to the table values, the beta coefficient is negative (B =-0.070), the interpretation is that for every 1-unit increase in the predictor variable, the outcome variable will decrease by the beta coefficient value. The negative means that as Communication increases and the dependent variable operational performance decreases. TVET Institutions in the NCP have operation performance increased by 0.458 with values for Employee Involvement and Continuous Improvement 0.352. Both Employee Involvement and Continuous Improvement were significant predictors of operational performance. However, Customer Focus and Communication were not significant predictors of operation performance.

5.6. Relationship between QMP and OP

5.6.1. Research Model

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + E$$

According to the Table 1-7 the value of R square is 0.778 and the prudent management of quality management practices accounts for revealing 77.8% of variability in Operational Performance. This is an indication that the quality practices play a significant role in determining the operational performance of TVET institutions in the NCP. The value of the adjusted R square is 0.773. This adjusted measure indicates 77.3% of the variability in the operational performance of Institutions due to the fitted model. The analysis of variance is used for testing whether the model is fitting for prediction.

5.7. Discussing the Results with Study Hypothesis

The below Table 1-8 shows the relationships between each independent variables and dependent variables, and these are hypothetically proved. According to the Table 1-8, all hypotheses were accepted in correlation, but few were supported in regression.

Table 1-8 Summary of the hypothesis

Hypothesis	Name of the hypothesis	Correlation	Results
H1	The Quality Management Practices has a relationship with the Operational Performance of TVET institutions in NCP	(Positive and strong relationship and Significant)	Accepted
H1a	The Employee Involvement has a relationship with the Operational Performance of TVET institutions in NCP	(Positive and strong relationship and Significant)	Accepted
H1b	The Continuous Improvement has a relationship with the Operational Performance of TVET institutions in NCP	(Positive and strong relationship and Significant)	Accepted
H1c	The Communication has a relationship with the Operational Performance of TVET institutions in NCP	(Positive and moderate relationship and Significant)	Accepted
H1d	The Customer focus has a relationship with the Operational Performance of TVET institutions in NCP	(Positive and moderate relationship and Significant)	Accepted

(Source: Author compilation)

According to the Table 1-8 the first hypothesis (**H1**), is the relationship between the Quality Management Practices and Operational Performance which is recorded at 0.842, therefore there is a strong relationship. In addition, Quality Management Practices explain a 70.8 % of the variation in Operational Performance. The research hypothesis (**H1**) that there was a relationship between the variables was accepted. However, according to multiple regression the variable is significant ($p \text{ value}=0.00<0.05$) and the variable was supported.

The second hypothesis (**H1a**) is the connection between the Employee Involvement and Operational Performance which is recorded at 0.830 as a result there is a strong relationship. In addition, Employee Involvement explains a 68.8% of the variation in Operational Performance. The research hypothesis H1a that there was a relationship between the variables was accepted. However, according to Table 1-8 under multiple regression variable is significant ($p \text{ value}=0.00<0.05$) and supported.

The third hypothesis (**H1b**) has a relationship between the Continuous Improvement and Operational Performance which is recorded at 0.758; therefore there is a moderate relationship. In addition, Continuous Improvement explains a 57.2% of the variation in Operational performance. The research hypothesis H1b that there was a relationship between the variables was accepted. However, according to a multiple regression variable is significant ($p \text{ value}=0.00<0.05$) and supported.

The fourth hypothesis (**H1c**) has a relationship between the Communication and Operational Performance which is recorded at 0.638; therefore there is a moderate relationship. In addition, Communication explains a 40.5% of the variation in Operational Performance. But according to the multiple regression variable is not significant ($p \text{ value}=0.213>0.05$) and not supported.

The fifth hypothesis (**H1d**) has a relationship between the Customer Focus and Operational Performance recorded 0.635, thus there is a moderate relationship. Customer Focus explains also 40% of the variation in Operational Performance change. The research hypothesis that there was a relationship between the variables was accepted. But according to the multiple regression variable is not significant ($p \text{ value}=0.329>0.05$) and not supported.

VI. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1. Conclusion

Continuous Improvement and Employee Involvement variables are significant predictors and communication and customer focus variables are not significant predictors. Finally, important thing can say with this study that there is an influence of implementation of quality management practices on the operational performance of TVET in the NCP. Nevertheless, some quality management practices such as Continuous Improvement and Employee Involvement have higher influence on operational performance on operational performance. They have statistically significant good relationships with the operational performance of TVET institutions. Other quality management practices such as Communication and Customer Focus have little influence on operational performance. They have statistically not significant good relationships with the operational performance.

6.2. Discussion on Objectives

1. However, according to the simple linear regression analysis, there is a strong relationship between quality management practices (QMP) and Operational Performance are significant ($p<0.05$). Therefore, there is a relationship between Operational Performance and Quality Management Practices variables. The correlation coefficient for the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable was 0.842, which characterized as a relationship..
2. Customer Focus is not a significant predictor. There is a little influence of quality management practice Customer Focus to the operational performance of TVET institutions in the NCP.
3. The research hypotheses that there was a relationship between the variables were accepted. However, according to the multiple regression analysis, although there is a moderate relationship between Communication and Operational Performance but it is not significant ($p<0.05$). Communication is not a significant predictor. But according to the analysis, values, the beta coefficient is negative ($B = -0.070$), therefore the explanation is that for every 1-unit increase in the predictor variable, the outcome variable will decrease. The negative means that as Communication variable increases and the dependent variable operational performance decreases.

4. Employee Involvement is a significant predictor. Study results show that employee involvement has the highest contribution to the operational performance. There is a high influence of quality management practice Employee Involvement to operational performance.
5. According to the multiple regression analysis, there is a moderate relationship between Continuous Improvement and Operational Performance. It is significant ($p < 0.05$). Continuous Improvement is also a significant predictor. There is a high influence of quality management practice Continuous Improvement to operational performance.
6. There are differences in the relationships between Operational Performance and demographic factors such as gender, age, education level, distance to center from home. They show that there are clear differences in these categories and others are not. This means demographic factors can consider predicting operational performance.

6.3. Recommendations with research study

1. It is recommended that the institutions should focus on students and ensure their needs to be met. Not only that need consider to give students to involve in the decision making process at the institution and should use the proper student feedback mechanism in the institutes to improve the operational performance.,
2. This study, therefore, recommends that an organization's management should improve the internal communication with employees and students of the institutes. A good appropriate communication system will allow easy flow of quality information to all levels in the organization. According to the search study results, Communication is not a very important factor when students consider about operational performance, but they expect more on continuing improvement and employee involvement in their institutions. Therefore, communication should be improved to get good operational performance in these institutions.
3. Student service quality also should be improved in the institutions. Therefore, to do that main thing should be improved that students' training materials are readily available and delivered on time in the institutions.
4. Male students have high satisfaction and they accepted the service quality than female students. It is recommended to consider improving the satisfaction of the female students by giving good sanitary facilities and classroom environment.
5. It is recommended for management to ensure students' views and suggestions are being made available to improve the present process of the institution.
6. It is recommended for institute's management to ensure employees are trained and also training should be conducted at all levels in the institution to make employees with highly knowledgeable about the needs of the students.
7. There is a need for the technical and vocational education and training institutions in the NCP to implement good QMP in the organizations to enhance the operational performance of TVET institutions. The TVET institutions should have a strategy to improve communication and customer focus of the organization. In addition, the organization's management commitment to service quality and student satisfaction should have a higher priority in the organization.

6.4. Limitations of the study

This research study focus on operations performance was measured by factors using customer satisfaction, quality of service. The quality management practices are taken only four factors such as Customer Focus, Employee Involvement, Communication and Continuous Improvement, but there are more on TQM practices. This research study focuses only on TVET in the NCP. The research study operates only for TVET institutions in Anuradhapura and Polonnaruwa Districts, therefore the findings can be generalized only for the rest of the districts.

6.5. Suggestions for further research studies

Suggestions for further research studies can be identified as they should be conducted on the same topic but in other provinces in Sri Lanka. Additionally, a study should be carried out to determine critical success factors that influence the operational performance of TVET the institutions. Also suggest the study should be conducted on the same topic, but to determine if there is a finding the Influence of Implementation of TQM practices on the operational performance of TVET institutions in Sri Lanka. Also the study should exploit in-depth information to highlight the influence and an effective of TQM practices implementation to improve organizational performance.

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